

Physics exploration with the LHCb experiment

LHCb Group in Brazil

Thematic area(s):

Instrumentation and Computing

Electroweak Physics, Flavor Physics and CP-violation

Strong Interactions

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Abstract

This document summarizes the participation of the Brazilian institutes in the LHCb experiment during the next 15 years. We focus on the expected challenges and costs to maintain and improve these contributions.

1 Introduction and Scientific Context

Researchers from Brazilian institutes are members of the LHCb collaboration since 1998 [1], participating on the conception, construction and operation of the experiment. Precise and novel measurements were performed since the detector started collecting data in 2010, including CP -violating phases in B and D hadron decays, lepton flavour violation tests, probes of QCD/EW in the forward region and searches for unknown physics.

Currently, the detector is being upgraded in order to reach unprecedented precision on the studies of b and c -quark sectors [2]. This is called LHCb Upgrade I-a and there will a modest upgrade in 2025, called LHCb Upgrade I-b. Another major upgrade is proposed to take place in 2030 [3], LHCb Upgrade II. These upgrades are motivated to provide complementary approaches of the energy and intensity frontier in the search for physics beyond the Standard Model [4].

This document will address the motivation and the challenges faced by the researchers of the Brazilian institutes to participate in the LHCb collaboration.

2 Methodology

During its 20-years long participation in LHCb, the Brazilian team gave several crucial contributions, with key roles in the development, installation and commissioning of the Muon System, notably in the readout electronics, multi-wire proportional chamber design and characterization, and experiment control system. The Brazilian groups developed the first muon identification algorithms that played a major role in LHCb flagship measurements. Brazil gave important contributions also in trigger (L0 and HLT), and computing. Brazilian physicists are contributing substantially to several physics analysis projects.

The Brazilian team is involved in the development of two new subdetectors for the LHCb upgrade and the real-time analysis technology which will be installed during the Long Shutdown 2 of LHC in 2019-2021.

3 List of the interested scientists in the community

Researcher	Institution
Alberto Reis	CBPF
André Massafferri	CBPF
Álvaro Gomes	CBPF / UFTM
Bruno S. de Paula	UFRJ
Carla Göbel	PUC-Rio
Érica Polycarpo	UFRJ
Fernando Rodrigues	UFRJ
Ignacio Bediaga	CBPF
Irina Nasteva	UFRJ
José Helder Lopes	UFRJ
Juan Otalora	UFRJ

Jussara Miranda	CBPF
Leandro de Paula	UFRJ
Melissa Cruz	CBPF / UAH
Miriam Gandelman	UFRJ
Murilo Rangel	UFRJ
Sandra Amato	UFRJ

4 Current status and expected challenges

The Brazilian institutes have been contributing to the LHCb experiment in different projects and in the best way possible. Although it would be fair to list the successful results of these contributions despite the adversities, we will describe below only the expected challenges.

It is common in Europe and in the USA that the financial agencies approve grants for the participation of each group in a large experiment and the contributions to given upgrades of these experiments. This method has been proven to be efficient since it provides a long-term commitment of the institutes. We believe that is the biggest challenge our institutes have and will have in the future. We propose that this demand should be highest priority of this strategy group.

As a consequence of the challenge listed above, there is difficulty to perform detector research and development (R&D) in the institutes due to the lack of infrastructure and engineering capabilities. In addition to this, a particle physicist is required to have a wide range of skills and knowledge and most of them are acquired in R&D laboratories. Therefore, we are often not able to properly train our students in the local institutes.

In addition, Brazilian institutes are not able to attract researchers from around the world. This issue is related to the lack of post-doc positions and the current funding strategy. A long-term grant would allow the institutes to hire post-docs with good salaries and with the possibility to be based at CERN.

5 Timeline

We plan to participate in the experiment operations until 2031. If the LHCb Upgrade II is approved to collect data during the High Luminosity LHC (HL-LHC) operational period, the timeline would be extended by at least five years.

6 Construction and operational costs

The operation cost (M&O) of the LHCb experiment is around 6 kCHF/year for each researcher with a PhD. Taking into account only the permanent scientists, the cost of the Brazilian institutes to be members of the LHCb collaboration is about 102 kCHF. Adding two post-doctoral researchers, the cost increases to 124 kCHF.

The LHCb Upgrade I will be completed in the next year and additional financial support is expected from institutes. The LHCb Upgrade II is expected to be approved soon. The cost to make a significant contribution to LHCb upgrades must be sizable and

predictable. It is very hard to give a scale but we propose a cost of one third of the M&O in 15 years, i.e., 620 kCHF in total.

A crucial part of the upgrade and operational costs is the financial support for mission trips to CERN. Historically, Brazil institutes do not formalize commitments to LHC experiments due to several limitations in the Brazilian research financial support system. This is mitigated by the person-power contributions which are only possible if there is financial support. In fact, dedicated mobility projects were created to support these trips, HELEN and EPLANET. Unfortunately, since 2015 there is no similar initiative and this has caused a clear negative impact on the participation of Brazilian institutes at CERN. We assume that we need ten trips of ten days per year with a cost of 25 kCHF per year, which is about 20% of the M&O cost.

In summary, the costs to maintain a fruitful collaboration with the LHCb experiment, the Brazilian institutes need 2855 kCHF in the next 15 years.

- [1] LHCb collaboration, *LHCb magnet: Technical Design Report*, CERN-LHCC-2000-007, 2000.
- [2] LHCb collaboration, *Framework TDR for the LHCb Upgrade: Technical Design Report*, CERN-LHCC-2012-007, 2012.
- [3] LHCb collaboration, *Expression of Interest for a Phase-II LHCb Upgrade: Opportunities in flavour physics, and beyond, in the HL-LHC era*, CERN-LHCC-2017-003, 2017.
- [4] LHCb collaboration, *Physics case for an LHCb Upgrade II — Opportunities in flavour physics, and beyond, in the HL-LHC era*, [arXiv:1808.08865](https://arxiv.org/abs/1808.08865).